

A Research on Glass Ceiling Syndrome Career Barriers of Women Academics

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Abstract—Although women have merit in their jobs, they still are located very few in the top management in many sectors. There are many causes of such situation. Such a situation creates obstacles; especially invisible ones are called “glass ceiling syndrome”. Also, studies which handle this subject in academic community are very few. The aim of this research is to reach the results about glass ceiling obstacles in terms of female teaching staff (academics) working in higher education institutions. To this end, our study was performed on female academics working at Selçuk University, Konya / Turkey. Our study's main aim can be expressed as to determine whether there are glass ceiling obstacles for female academics working at the higher education institution in question, to measure their glass ceiling perceptions and, thus, to identify what the glass ceiling barrier components for them to promotion to senior management positions are.

Keywords—Career, Career Barriers, Glass ceiling syndrome.

I. INTRODUCTION

RAPID changes in information, technology and human resources today and the global competition cause a rapid change in business life as well. In this global competitive environment, the most important element, that makes difference between organizations and creates superiority, is human resources. To catch up with the speed of changes and developments in business life and to keep up with the time are possible with managing human resources well and creating a labor force happy in business life and pleased of job. One of the important issues in getting this result is career and career management phenomenon. Therefore, in recent years, current career management practices have been raised and for human resources especially career obstacles have been started being investigated. In this context, career obstacles have been assessed to be investigated separately especially for men and women workers.

II. CAREER CONCEPT AND ITS SCOPE

The dictionary meaning of the “career” is stone quarry, racecourse and arena [1]. The concept, that began to attract attention in the 1970s firstly, describes a life-long pursuit in general. In the specific sense, it means the deal that is started at early ages with the expectation of making progress and rising and continued as a principle until retirement [2]. Much

more specifically, the career concept describes that the individual's rising upwards in the hierarchical terms in occupational field in which is decided by individual and having more fees, prestige and status in this direction [3].

Career concept is a process involving hierarchical positions, work and attitudes and behaviors that one has throughout their business life [4]. The concept which is defined with the words such as success in everyday life, promotion, status and often used as synonymous with occupation is insufficient to explain the career phenomenon. Career concept, beyond this definition, includes much wider meanings [5]. The concept is also in use for the statuses such as housewives, mothers and fathers. In organizations, regardless of work or status, it covers the range of work all the employees do during their working lives [6].

III. CAREER MANAGEMENT AND CAREER PLANNING

Career management, with its simplest meaning, makes planning regarding to individuals' business or professional lives. The importance of career management in terms of HRM is to ensure mobility of employees within the organization and thus is motivated. Those who are working for business organizations in which career management is done can know or predict the place or status how long later they can reach. This forecast or estimate is very important because it connects employees to work and organization provides motivation, provides integration with the institution preventing other pursuits. Career management is a useful and necessary study in terms of the employees' awareness of their positions, realizing what is waiting for them in next stage, foreseeing their own professional future, making proper preparation according to the course of progress, in short, in terms of preparing themselves for the future [7].

Career planning is a component of career management [8]. Career planning is a problem-solving and decision-making process. Individual and organization work together during this process. In the process, firstly, the individual's personal interests and abilities are determined, his/her performance of working together is evaluated and the required qualifications planned for one will need throughout his/her business career are determined [9]. Career planning has two important dimensions including individual and organizational. Individual career planning focuses on the individual more rather than the works itself, it makes an analysis of individual's purposes and abilities. With individual career planning, an activity process comprising of individual's own evaluation of his/her capabilities and interests, his/her investigation of career opportunities, establishing his/her career goals and detecting

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methods that lead him/her to these goals is expressed [10]. In short, career planning is an individual process and it describes the one's choice regarding business paths he/she will proceed [11]. Organizational career planning is the process of creating career paths and activities toward the individual within the organization. Organizations do career planning both meeting the needs of current and future qualified employees, and in order to help employees' career expectations and achieving their career goals. Thus, it is important and necessary that organizational career planning and individual career planning are in the same direction [12]. As a result, individual career planning and organizational career planning are not separated and not a different functions from each other. The most important factor for the career planning to be successful is the support from the management. Beside the individual's expectations, if the organization helps the employee with this subject taking its own needs into account, they meet both the organizational needs and the employees' needs [13].

IV. GLASS CEILING SYNDROME AND ITS SCOPE

The glass ceiling syndrome, which was used in an article published by Nora Frenkiel in *Adweek* magazine in 1984 for the first time, however, became popular with the article titled "Woman in Business Life" published in the *Wall Street Journal* by Hymowitz and Schellhardt in 1986, often started to be used also in academic field in the 1990s [14].

The glass ceiling term is a metaphor used for revealing inequality in a workplace; it describes hidden barriers that prevent women from reaching the top positions in an institution [15]. The concept expresses only inability to rise because of being a woman, but not an individual inability to rise [16]. Glass ceiling expresses obstacles located between female employees and upper management levels, regardless their successes and merits, invisible, transparent and at the same time insurmountable obstacles [17]. In other words, the glass ceiling is artificial obstacles, which prevent women from reaching the top management, created by organizational prejudices and patterns associated with attitude. Therefore, women are prevented after arriving in a certain level, their promotion to the top management is blocked, and they are kept away from management staffs due to some reasons and prejudices that are not exactly called [18].

Glass ceiling is a career obstacle causes them to be stuck in some levels that can be said their middle career. They are "invisible obstacle" that prevents them from reaching top management tasks. In formation and continuation of this phenomenon, the presence of masculine organizational culture is the most important factor. Establishing organizations based on beliefs and rules adopted by men bring some kind of hidden prejudices with itself [19]. The lack of women workers that show a successful senior manager profile and employing women in middle-level jobs more in organizations lends support to the prejudices against women [20]. Again, the view that their leaving jobs are normal or more likely is effective in the formation of this phenomenon due to having children and their responsibilities in the family [21]. Glass ceiling

syndrome is a fact not in only developing countries but also in developed countries.

The concept of the glass ceiling does not cover only promotion or advancement in the hierarchy, but also refers to inequality in income distribution, implementation, supervision and using initiative. Therefore, glass ceiling is the general name of career barriers faced by women in social life [22]. There are many barriers in front of women to senior executive positions. These barriers generally can be divided into three categories as individual, organizational and social. Assuming multi-role -role and level of responsibility woman assume such as mother, wife and being a employee worker and etc. role and responsibility role level- and individual preference and perceptions -lack of confidence, indecisiveness, not improving themselves, not risking challenges in career and not preferring promotion- are the obstacles from individual factors [23]. Organization's existing culture, lack of politics, mentor -advisor, supporter, guide- and inability to participate in unofficial communication networks are obstacles stemming from organizational factors [24], [25]. Barriers arising from social factors can be said professional distinction and stereotypes [26].

Women can benefit from some strategies in order to break the glass ceiling barriers to advance in their careers. Lockwood [27] states that women's working harder than other employees, showing higher performance especially than their male competitors is an effective strategy to break the glass ceiling. Thus, thanks to high-performance, female employees will be able to prove themselves to others. Improving their education level and developing their professional skills are can be considered as an important strategy to break down prejudices they face in the male-dominated business world. In fact, this aspect is an important starting in blocking the glass ceiling [28]. Again, implementation of career development programs for women willing to make a career and are talented lead them do feel ready for the top management staff so they acquire necessary managerial skills and glass ceiling barriers will be prevented. In this way, the organization can also utilize the potential employees [29]. On the other hand, mentoring is an important tool in providing career support for women. Mentors perform their task of training and routing others by transferring their knowledge and experiences to other individuals. Mentors, who advise women to overcome the difficulties they will encounter, are a good way of strategy [30]. Finally, developing social networks is a common individual strategy that can be used by women. Developing acceptable business behaviors by men, not staying away from men relationship network is an important step in the process of career progression [31].

V. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Purpose and Importance of Research

National and international researches reveal that women can still take places in management positions very less even being had worked in their jobs for long years and despite having seniority. Such situations, which prevent women from

reaching top positions, have several reasons and are invisible in nature, are called "glass ceiling syndrome". National studies on the subject are very limited compared to the ones conducted abroad. Also, studies examining the subject academically are very few. The purpose of this study is to reach results about the glass ceiling obstacles in terms of female academics working in higher education institutions. To this end, our study was performed on women working at Selcuk University -Konya/Turkey-. Therefore, to determine if there are glass ceiling barriers for the women academics working on the higher education institution in question, measuring their glass ceiling perceptions and thus, identifying the glass ceiling components preventing them from reaching to top management positions can be expressed as the main purpose of our research.

B. Research Methodology

In our study, a questionnaire was used as data collection tool. In the preparation of the questionnaire, has benefited from studies conducted on the subject. The questionnaire consists of two parts. The first part consists of demographic questions on women academics that are subject to the survey. The second part consists of questions, intended for the glass ceiling syndrome, prepared according to 5-point Likert scale. The questions in this part are identified under 7 factors such as assuming multi-role, women academics' individual preference perceptions, organizational culture and organizational policy, inability to participate in unofficial communication networks, lack of mentors, occupational discrimination and stereotypes.

The main mass of our research is constituted of women academics working in academic units of the University of Selcuk. As the period we carried out the study, the number of women academic staff working at the university is 441. Our research was conducted on 50 academic staff of 65 women we chose randomly. The information obtained by the questionnaire was analyzed using SPSS 20 software package programme on computer. In the evaluation of demographic data related to the female academics subject to our research, frequency distribution, scale evaluation and interpretation of results, the average and standard deviation values were utilized. The independent t-test and Oneway ANOVA was used for determining whether the candidates differ in demographic variables.

C. Hypothesis of the Study

- H1.** According to marital status of female academics, there is a significant difference between the perceptions of the glass ceiling.
- H2.** According to the titles of female academics, there is a significant difference between the perceptions of the glass ceiling.
- H3.** According to female academics' ages, there is a significant difference between the perceptions of the glass ceiling.
- H4.** According to female academics' having children, there is a significant difference between the perceptions of the glass ceiling.

- H5.** According to female academics' professional experiences, there is a significant difference between the perceptions of the glass ceiling.

D. Research Findings and Evaluation

1. General Findings

All the findings related to demographic characteristics of female academics subject to our study are shown in the Table I:

TABLE I
DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF FEMALE ACADEMIC STAFF

Academic Title	Frequency	Percentage
Professor	8	0,16
Associate Professor	11	0,22
Assistant Professor	15	0,30
Research Assistant	9	0,18
Prelector	7	0,14
Age		
20-30	13	0,26
31-40	23	0,46
41-50	14	0,28
Marital Status		
Married	23	0,46
Single	27	0,54
Professional Experience		
1-5 years	15	0,30
6-10 years	10	0,20
11-15 years	12	0,24
16-20 years	10	0,20
21 + years	3	0,06
The number of children		
None	32	0,64
1	13	0,26
2 and more	5	0,25

As seen in Table I, 16% of respondents are Professor, 22% are Associate Professor, 30% are Assistant Professors, 18% are Research Assistants and 14% are Prelectors. Considering the age range; 26% of respondents are between the ages of 20-30, 46% are between the ages of 31-40 and 28% are between the 41-50 age ranges. 46% of the respondents are married, 54% are single. In terms of professional experience, 30% of the subjects have experience between 1-5 years, 20% between 6-10 years, 24% between 11-15 years, 20% between 16-20 years, and 6% over 21 years. Considering the number of children, the proportion of the subjects without children is 64%, 26% for 1 child, and 25% have more than 2 children.

2. Factor Analysis and Scale Reliability

Factor analysis was conducted in order to determine female academic staffs' level of perception of the glass ceiling. For testing if the data set suitable to the factor analysis, Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) sampling adequacy and Bartlett test of sphericity tests were applied. The data set was determined to be suitable for factor analysis with KMO value over 0,50 and Bartlett's test tail probability is significant at the 0.05 significance level.

KMO= 0,828

X² Bartlett: 1510,566

Test tail probability p: 0,000

KMO sampling adequacy test shows that the variables are suitable for factor analysis pointing to the homogeneous nature of the variables; and Bartlett test shows that correlation matrix of variables is at a significant appropriate level. The resulting data were subjected to factor analysis the determination of the glass ceiling subscales and the questions were analyzed using "Basic Components" (principal components), namely, varimax rotation. As a result of this factor analysis, no questions were removed from 37 Likert-scale questions. In the calculation of the internal consistency the factors, Cronbach's alpha coefficient was measured and scale reliability was identified as Cronbach's Alpha ($\alpha_{glass-ceiling_{syn.}}$) = 0.792. After all, 7 dimensions were obtained. Factors, respectively; multi-role assuming, women's perceptions of personal preference, organizational culture and organizational policy, inability to participate in unofficial communication networks, lack of mentors, professional discrimination and stereotypes. These dimensions' percentage (total variance) of explaining the concept of the glass ceiling was found as 61.815%, and internal consistency coefficient of all inventories was found as 0.83.

3. Field Related Results

a) Results Explaining Glass-Ceiling Barriers According to Female Academics Marital Status

H0. According to female academics' marital status, there is no significant difference between the perceptions of the glass ceiling.

H1. According to female academics' marital status, there is a significant difference between the perceptions of the glass ceiling.

perceptions and marital status ($F=0.001$, $p>0.05$), between mentor deficiency variable and marital status ($F=0.000$, $p>0.05$), between occupational discrimination variable and marital status ($F=2.556$, $p>0.05$), between stereotypes variables and marital status ($F=0.367$, $p>0.05$), between the variable of inability to participate in informal communication networks and marital status ($F=0.350$, $p>0.05$) no significant differences were observed. According to these results, the rejected hypothesis H0 is accepted according to factors related to women academics' perceptions of the glass ceiling.

b) Explaining Results of Glass-Ceiling Barriers According to Female Academics' Professional Titles

H0. According to female academics' titles, there is no significant difference between the perceptions of the glass ceiling.

H1. According to female academics' marital status, there is a significant difference between the perceptions of the glass ceiling.

In general examination on Table III, because p value >0.05 , data is homogeneous and the model is seen to be significant. According to the results Onaway ANOVA test; between the responses to the items describing multi-role assuming variable and occupational titles of the participants ($F=1.361$, $p>0.05$); between the responses to the items describing the perceptions of personal preference variable and participants' occupational titles ($F=0.676$, $p>0.05$); between the responses to the items describing organizational culture and organizational policy variable and participants' occupational titles ($F=0.511$, $p>0.05$); between the responses to the items describing inability to participate in informal communication networks variable and participants' occupational titles ($F=0.634$, $p>0.05$); between the lack of mentor and participants' occupational titles ($F=0.261$, $p>0.05$); between the responses to the items describing occupational discrimination variable and participants' occupational titles ($F=1.527$, $p>0.05$) any significant differences were observed. Therefore, it arises that the surveyed subjects' perceptions and opinions about multi-role assuming, personal preference perceptions, organizational culture and organizational policy, inability to participate in informal communication networks, lack of mentors and occupational discrimination do not change according to occupational titles. However, when the responses to the items describing stereotypes variable and the participants' occupational titles are compared, it was seen that there was ($F=2.676$, $p<0.05$) a significant difference. According to this situation, the participants' opinions about stereotypes vary according to their occupational titles. As a result, according to these results, as H1 hypothesis is rejected according to multi-role assuming, personal preference perceptions, organizational culture and policy, inability to join unofficial communication networks, lack of mentors and occupational discrimination variables, according to stereotype variable it was accepted.

According to t test results, between multi-role assuming and marital status ($F=0.134$, $p>0.05$), between personal preference

TABLE II
FEMALE ACADEMICS' PERCEPTIONS OF GLASS CEILING ACCORDING TO MARITAL

Factors	Marital Status	n	X	S	P	f
Multi-Role Assuming	Married	23	3,1801	0,57502	0,134	0,079
	Single	27	2,8836	0,58773		
Personal Preference Perceptions	Married	23	3,0261	0,40589	0,184	0,971
	Single	27	3,0222	0,33893		
Organizational Culture and Organizational Policy	Married	23	2,8841	0,68798	0,001	0,062
	Single	27	3,2716	0,73837		
The Inability to Join Unofficial Communication Networks	Married	23	2,7971	0,68710	0,000	0,393
	Single	27	2,9753	0,76195		
Lack of Mentor	Married	23	3,1739	0,82032	2,556	0,443
	Single	27	3,4074	1,23286		
Occupational Discrimination	Married	23	2,4928	0,68068	0,367	0,627
	Single	27	2,5988	0,82852		
Stereotypes	Married	23	2,6033	0,64914	0,350	0,271
	Single	27	2,3843	2,72881		

TABLE III
FEMALE ACADEMICS' PERCEPTIONS OF GLASS CEILING ACCORDING TO THEIR PROFESSIONAL TITLES

Factor	Title	N	X	S	F	Levene Sig.	P
Multi-Role Assuming	Research Assistant	9	3,1126	0,54017	1,361	0,542	0,262
	Prelector	7	2,6122	0,88339			
	Assistant Professor	15	3,2857	0,20203			
	Associate Professor	11	3,0238	0,48164			
	Professor	8	2,6429	0,50508			
	Total	50	3,0200	0,59500			
Personal Preference Perceptions	Research Assistant	9	2,9818	0,29734	0,676	0,125	0,612
	Prelector	7	3,0286	0,31472			
	Assistant Professor	15	3,3000	0,14142			
	Associate Professor	11	3,0667	0,72296			
	Professor	8	3,3000	0,42426			
	Total	50	3,0240	0,36732			
Organizational Culture and Organizational Policy	Research Assistant	9	3,0404	0,64822	0,511	0,204	0,728
	Prelector	7	3,1905	0,80178			
	Assistant Professor	15	3,5833	0,82496			
	Associate Professor	11	3,2500	1,08909			
	Professor	8	2,6667	1,17851			
	Total	50	3,0933	0,73475			
Inability to Join Unofficial Communication Networks	Research Assistant	9	2,8384	0,66730	0,634	0,257	0,641
	Prelector	7	2,8571	0,74180			
	Assistant Professor	15	3,6667	0,47140			
	Associate Professor	11	3,0000	0,89443			
	Professor	8	2,8333	1,64992			
	Total	50	2,8933	0,72669			
Lack of Mentor	Research Assistant	9	3,2424	0,98521	0,261	0,042	0,901
	Prelector	7	3,1429	1,70084			
	Assistant Professor	15	3,7500	0,35355			
	Associate Professor	11	3,5833	0,97040			
	Professor	8	3,5000	0,70711			
	Total	50	3,3000	1,05946			
Occupational Discrimination	Research Assistant	9	2,6414	0,63344	1,527	0,141	0,211
	Prelector	7	2,4286	1,08379			
	Assistant Professor	15	3,3333	0,94281			
	Associate Professor	11	2,1111	0,63828			
	Professor	8	2,0000	1,41421			
	Total	50	2,5500	0,75836			
Stereotypes	Research Assistant	9	2,5114	0,61107	2,676	0,600	0,044
	Prelector	7	2,1429	0,85522			
	Assistant Professor	15	3,3750	0,88388			
	Associate Professor	11	2,7500	0,52440			
	Professor	8	1,5625	0,79550			
	Total	50	2,4850	0,69512			

c) The Results Describing the Glass Ceiling Barriers According to Female Academics' Age Group

H0. According to female academics' age groups, there is no significant difference between the perceptions of the glass ceiling.

H1. According to female academics' ages, there is a significant difference between the perceptions of the glass ceiling

As it is seen in the Table IV, it turned out that there is no significant difference between Multi-Role Assuming (F=2.504, p>0.05) from variables related participants' age groups and Personal Preference Perceptions (F=2.477, p>0.05), Inability to Join in Unofficial Communication

Networks (F=1.185, p>0.05), Lack of Mentors (F=1.209, p>0.05) and Organizational Culture, Organizational Policy (F=0.486, p>0.05). However, there is a significant difference between Occupational Discrimination (F=4.083, p<0.05) and Stereotypes (F=3.770 p<0.05). According to these results, while H1 hypothesis is rejected according to Multi-Role Assuming, Personal Preference Perceptions, Inability to Join in Unofficial Communication Networks, Lack of Mentors and Organizational Culture and Organizational Policy variables, it is accepted according to Occupational Discrimination and Stereotypes variables.

TABLE IV
 GLASS CEILING BARRIERS ACCORDING TO FEMALE ACADEMICS' AGE GROUPS

Factor	Age	N	X	S	F	Levene Sig.	P
Multi-Role Assuming	20-30	28	2,9337	0,59027	2,504	0,981	0,093
	31-40	14	3,3061	0,57378			
	41-50	8	2,8214	0,53316			
	Total	50	3,0200	0,59500			
Personal Preference Perceptions	20-30	28	2,9571	0,32821	2,477	0,333	0,095
	31-40	14	3,0143	0,31831			
	41-50	8	3,2750	0,50071			
	Total	50	3,0240	0,36732			
Organizational Culture and Organizational Policy	20-30	28	3,1845	0,76355	0,486	0,823	0,618
	31-40	14	2,9643	0,63441			
	41-50	8	3,0000	0,84045			
	Total	50	3,0933	0,73475			
Inability to Join in Unofficial Communication Networks	20-30	28	2,9881	0,72283	1,185	0,222	0,315
	31-40	14	2,9048	0,82097			
	41-50	8	2,5417	0,50198			
	Total	50	2,8933	0,72669			
Lack of Mentors	20-30	28	3,5000	1,04527	1,209	0,441	0,307
	31-40	14	3,1071	0,83617			
	41-50	8	2,9375	1,39994			
	Total	50	3,3000	1,05946			
Occupational Discrimination	20-30	28	2,7083	0,74897	4,083	0,565	0,023
	31-40	14	2,6071	0,66541			
	41-50	8	1,8958	0,66629			
	Total	50	2,5500	0,75836			
Stereotypes	20-30	28	2,4464	0,60230	3,770	0,110	0,030
	31-40	14	2,8214	0,62156			
	41-50	8	2,0313	0,89330			
	Total	50	2,4850	0,69512			

d) The Results Explaining the Glass Ceiling Barriers According Female Academics' Case of Having Children

H0. According to female academics' case of having children, there is no significant difference between the perceptions of the glass ceiling.

H1. According to female academics' case of having children, there is a significant difference between the perceptions of the glass ceiling.

When the responses given to the items explaining the variables related to the subjects' case of having children are compared, there is no significant difference between Multi-Role Assuming ($F=0.810$, $p>0.05$), Personal Preference Perceptions ($F=0.853$, $p>0.05$), Lack of Mentors ($F=3.143$, $p>0.05$), Occupational Discrimination ($F=1.735$, $p>0.05$), Organizational Culture and Policy ($F=1.030$, $p>0.05$), Stereotypes ($F=0.841$, $p>0.05$) and Inability to Join in Unofficial Communication Networks ($F=1.791$, $p>0.05$). According to these results, H1 hypothesis is rejected and H0 hypothesis is accepted.

TABLE V
FEMALE ACADEMICS' GLASS CEILING PERCEPTIONS ACCORDING TO THEIR CASE OF HAVING CHILDREN

Factor	Children	N	X	S	F	Leneve Sig.	p
Multi-Role Assuming	No Children	32	2,9420	0,59938			
	1	13	3,1868	0,62918			
	2	5	3,0857	0,46948	0,810	0,828	0,451
	Total	50	3,0200	0,59500			
Personal Preference Perceptions	No Children	32	2,9813	0,35327			
	1	13	3,0615	0,29872			
	2	5	3,2000	0,60000	0,853	0,440	0,432
	Total	50	3,0240	0,36732			
Organizational Culture and Organizational Policy	No Children	32	3,1927	0,74187			
	1	13	2,8462	0,52907			
	2	5	3,1000	1,10930	1,030	0,115	0,365
	Total	50	3,0933	0,73475			
Inability to Join in Unofficial Communication Networks	No Children	32	2,9271	0,76545			
	1	13	3,0256	0,64495			
	2	5	2,3333	0,47140	1,791	0,513	0,178
	Total	50	2,8933	0,72669			
Lack of Mentors	No Children	32	3,5156	0,98770			
	1	13	2,6923	1,07118			
	2	5	3,5000	1,06066	3,143	0,788	0,052
	Total	50	3,3000	1,05946			
Stereotypes	No Children	32	2,4180	0,65347			
	1	13	2,5096	0,86220			
	2	5	2,8500	0,41833	0,841	0,219	0,438
	Total	50	2,4850	0,69512			
Occupational Discrimination	No Children	32	2,6354	0,80815			
	1	13	2,5641	0,54662			
	2	5	1,9667	0,77639	1,735	0,435	0,188
	Total	50	2,5500	0,75836			

e) The Results Explaining the Glass Ceiling Barriers According to Female Academics' Professional Experiences

H0. According to the professional experience of women academics, there is no significant difference between the perceptions of the glass ceiling.

H1. According to the professional experience of women academics, there is a significant difference between the perceptions of the glass ceiling

When the responses to the items explaining Multi-Role Assuming ($F=1.365$, $p>0.05$) variable and the participants' Professional experiences are compared via ANOVA test, Personal Preference Perceptions ($F=1.382$, $p>0.05$), Organizational Culture and Organizational Policy ($F=0.096$, $p>0.05$), Inability to Join in Unofficial Communication Networks ($F=0.797$, $p>0.05$), Lack of Mentors ($F=2.449$, $p>0.05$), Occupational Discrimination ($F=2.016$, $p>0.05$), Stereotypes ($F=1.524$, $p>0.05$) were seen that there is no significant difference. Accordingly, H0 hypothesis is accepted.

TABLE VI
FEMALE ACADEMICS' GLASS CEILING PERCEPTIONS ACCORDING TO THEIR PROFESSIONAL STATUS

Factor	Experience	N	X	S	F	Leneve Sig.	p
Multi-Role Assuming	1-5	15	2,9409	0,60551	1,365	0,442	0,261
	6-10	10	3,0714	0,53261			
	11-15	12	3,3333	0,66240			
	16-20	10	3,3571	0,10102			
	21 and Above	3	2,6429	0,29738			
	Total	50	3,0200	0,59500			
Personal Preference Perceptions	1-5	15	2,9655	0,32544	1,382	0,262	0,255
	6-10	10	2,9667	0,34448			
	11-15	12	3,0889	0,33333			
	16-20	10	3,0000	0,28284			
	21 and Above	3	3,4000	0,67330			
	Total	50	3,0240	0,36732			
Organizational Culture and Organizational Policy	1-5	15	3,2126	0,74522	0,096	0,614	0,419
	6-10	10	3,0278	0,62731			
	11-15	12	2,7407	0,57802			
	16-20	10	2,6667	0,47140			
	21 and Above	3	3,3333	1,13855			
	Total	50	3,0933	0,73475			
Inability to Join in Unofficial Communication Networks	1-5	15	2,9885	0,72091	0,797	0,902	0,533
	6-10	10	3,0000	0,69921			
	11-15	12	2,7778	0,83333			
	16-20	10	2,8333	0,70711			
	21 and Above	3	2,3333	0,60858			
	Total	50	2,8933	0,72669			
Lack of Mentors	1-5	15	3,4655	1,06847	2,449	0,322	0,060
	6-10	10	3,5000	,54772			
	11-15	12	2,3889	1,02402			
	16-20	10	3,2500	1,06066			
	21 and Above	3	3,8750	0,85391			
	Total	50	3,3000	1,05946			
Stereotypes	1-5	15	2,4526	0,60079	1,524	0,199	0,211
	6-10	10	2,3750	0,48088			
	11-15	12	2,5556	0,94603			
	16-20	10	3,5625	0,61872			
	21 and Above	3	2,1875	0,82601			
	Total	50	2,4850	0,69512			
Occupational Discrimination	1-5	15	2,7299	0,72841	2,016	0,925	0,108
	6-10	10	2,7778	0,76497			
	11-15	12	2,1481	0,59771			
	16-20	10	2,2500	0,58926			
	21 and Above	3	1,9583	0,98484			
	Total	50	2,5500	0,75836			

VI. CONCLUSION

This research was conducted to determine whether there are glass ceiling barriers for female academics and to determine the glass ceiling components preventing them from promoting to top managerial positions. According to research findings, female academics' perceptions of glass ceiling do not show any significant differences statistically according to Multi-Role Assuming, Personal Preference Perceptions, Organizational Culture and Organizational Policy, Lack of Mentors, Stereotypes, Occupational Discrimination Inability to Join in Unofficial Communication Networks Factor.

When professional title variable is analyzed, while there is no significant difference among female lecturers' glass ceiling

perceptions according to Multi-Role Assuming, Personal Preference Perceptions, Organizational Culture and Organizational Policy, Inability to Join in Unofficial Communication Networks, Lack of Mentors and Occupational Discrimination variables, it is statically significant according to Stereotypes variable. In the study, Assistant Professors' glass ceiling perceptions were found more than Associate Professors'.

When the age variable is analyzed, while there is no significant difference among female lecturers' glass ceiling syndrome perceptions according to Multi-Role Assuming, Personal Preference Perceptions, Organizational Culture and Organizational Policy, Inability to Join in Unofficial Communication Networks, Lack of Mentors variables, a

significant difference was reached according to Occupational Discrimination and Stereotypes variables. Perceptions of the glass ceiling in the age group 31-40 academics were obtained higher than 41-50 age groups. The Occupational Discrimination levels of academics in the age group 20-30 were concluded as higher than 41-50 age groups.

No significant difference was reached statically between female lecturers' case of having children and their glass ceiling perceptions. Again, no significant difference was obtained among the lecturers' glass ceiling perceptions according to their professional experiences.

In addition, the majority of subjects who participated in our survey stated that, regarding to Multi-Role Assuming, their place is not beside their husbands, their priority is to take care of their children, they have more responsibility than men in the family, academic life doesn't prevent being a good wife and mother, their first priority is not the academic career and marriage hampers academic studies.

Regarding to Personal Preference Perceptions, the subjects think that they do not like being managed rather than managing, serving as senior executives does not affect their personality negatively in terms of gender, they have specific plans to achieve their career goals and they have necessary skills to be a successful manager, but they do not have enough time to be a successful manager.

Regarding to the organizational culture and policy, the subjects expressed that they may be exposed to discrimination about selection of courses and academic advancement, more opportunities are created for males in senior management positions, work places are governed by the rules of men and they cannot communicate with male managers comfortably.

About Inability to Join in Unofficial Communication Networks, the subjects have the opinion of that they do not have difficulties to join the communication networks dominated by men.

About Lack of Mentors, the subjects are of the opinion that there aren't enough female managers that can be role models for them, they cannot utilize enough of mentor relationship and they are not directed to the jobs suitable for women.

Regarding to occupational discrimination, the subjects pointed out that workplace task distributions do not show difference for women and men, they do not need to work harder and wait for longer than men in order to advance and rise in their jobs, they do not agree with the idea that they cannot have enough places in effective tasks to reach senior executive levels and only men are suitable for senior executive positions.

Regarding to stereotypes, the participants stated that they are as much bonded as men to their career, they can make quick and logical decisions, they are as resistant as men against work-life challenges but they do not like long hours of work and they do not agree with the idea that they cannot be successful in senior executive positions because of being more emotional than men.

Glass ceiling constitutes barriers women face especially about promotion. However, according to research results, it can be said that female lecturers do not face glass ceiling

barriers as much as other job groups. In our country, women face with generally gender-based obstacles. Basically, to overcome these obstacles will be possible with the change of the values determining a woman's place in the society into supporting woman to enter work life.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. S. Simsek, and S. Oge, *Human Resource Management*, Extended 4th Edition, Konya: Egitim Publications, 2011.
- [2] Resat Yazıcı, *Human Relations and Personnel Management*, Ankara: Semih Ofset, 1987.
- [3] J. Walton, *Strategic Human Resource Development*, Prentice Hall.
- [4] Sibel Yavuz, "An Example of Career Management and Application in Business", *Marmara University, Institute of Social Sciences, Department of Labor Economics and Work Psychology*, Unpublished Master Thesis, İstanbul, 2006.
- [5] M. A. Ozer, *Managements and Managers in the 21st Century*, 2nd Edition, Ankara: Nobel Publications, 2011.
- [6] Sibel Yavuz, "An Example of Career Management and Application in Business", *Marmara University, Institute of Social Sciences, Department of Labor Economics and Work Psychology*, Unpublished Master Thesis, İstanbul, 2006.
- [7] İlhami Findıkcı, *Human Resources Management*, 4th Edition, İstanbul: Alfa Publications, 1999.
- [8] Halil Can, *Organization and Management*, Ankara: Adım Publications, 1992.
- [9] J. G. Loongenecker and C. D. Pringle, *Management*, 5th Edition, 1981.
- [10] Fatih Karcioglu, *Career Management*, İstanbul: Karizma Publications, 2001.
- [11] Cavide Uyargil, Z. Adal, I. D. Ataay and et all., *Human Resource Management*, 3th Edition, İstanbul: Beta Publications, 2008.
- [12] Dursun Bingol, *Human Resource Management*, 5th Edition, İstanbul: Beta Publications, 2003.
- [13] M. A. Ozer, *Managements and Managers in the 21st Century*, 2nd Edition, Ankara: Nobel Publications, 2011.
- [14] Nancy Lockwood, "The Glass Ceiling: Domestic and International Perspectives", *Research Quarterly*, USA, pp. 1-10, 2004.
- [15] Janeen Baxter and E. O. Wright, "The Glass Ceiling Hypothesis a Comparative Study Of The United States, Sweden and Australia", *Gender & Society*, Vol: 14, Ed: 2, pp. 275-294, 2000.
- [16] Evrim Mayaturk, "Gender Based Discrimination in Working Life and an Application", *Dokuz Eylul University, Institute of Social Sciences*, Unpublished Master Thesis, İzmir, 2006.
- [17] Duygu Guldal, "A Study on Identifying The Factors Motivating and Demotivating Women Managers", *Cukurova University, Institute of Social Sciences*, Unpublished Master Thesis, Adana, 2006.
- [18] Sule Aydın, E. Ozkul, G. K. Tandoğan, N. Sahin, "A Study on Glass Ceiling Effect on Promoting Women to Senior and Top Management in Hotel Businesses", *XV. The Book of Declaration of National Management and Organization Congress*, 25-27 May., pp. 312-319, Sakarya, 2007.
- [19] Volkan Isik, "Gender Discrimination Applications Against Women Workforce in Business Life", *Journal of Social Policy in Public*, 11. Edition, pp. 67-72, Ankara, 2009.
- [20] Mimar Turkkahraman, and Kamil Sahin, "Woman and Career", *Alanya Journal of Business Faculty*, Vol: 2, Ed: 1, pp.75-88, Alanya, 2010.
- [21] Evrim Mayaturk, "Gender Based Discrimination in Working Life and an Application", *Dokuz Eylul University, Institute of Social Sciences*, Unpublished Master Thesis, İzmir, 2006.
- [22] Asli Ozturk, "A Study on the Glass Ceiling Syndrome of Female Lecturers: The Sample Of Ankara University", *Gazi University, Institute of Educational Sciences Department of the Office of Management Science*, Unpublished Master Thesis, Ankara, 2011.
- [23] Ayse Karaca, "Career Barriers of Female Managers: An Applied Research on Glass Ceiling Syndrome", *Selçuk University, Institute of Social Sciences*, Unpublished Master Thesis, Konya, 2007.
- [24] Asli Ozturk, "A Study on the Glass Ceiling Syndrome of Female Lecturers: The Sample Of Ankara University", *Gazi University, Institute of Educational Sciences Department of the Office of Management Science*, Unpublished Master Thesis, Ankara, 2011.

- [25] Ayse Karaca, "Career Barriers of Female Managers: An Applied Research on Glass Ceiling Syndrome", *Selçuk University, Institute of Social Sciences*, Unpublished Master Thesis, Konya, 2007.
- [26] Ercan Taskin, and Ayfer Cetin, "Women Managers Glass Ceiling Effects on Perception Strategies to Overcome the Glass Ceiling: The Case of Bursa", *Dumlupinar University Journal of Social Sciences*, 33. Editin, pp. 19-34, Sakarya, 2012.
- [27] Nancy Lockwood, "The Glass Ceiling: Domestic and International Perspectives", *Research Quarterly*, USA, p. 4, 2004
- [28] Asli Ozturk, "A Study on the Glass Ceiling Syndrome of Female Lecturers: The Sample Of Ankara University", *Gazi University, Institute of Educational Sciences Department of the Office of Management Science*, Unpublished Master Thesis, Ankara, 2011.
- [29] Bayram Sezen, "Glass Ceiling Barrier Women Employees Face With in Organizations: A Research On Medium and Large-Scale Hotel Businesses", *18 Mart University, Institute of Social Sciences*, Unpublished Master Thesis, Canakkale, 2008.
- [30] Asli Ozturk, "A Study on the Glass Ceiling Syndrome of Female Lecturers: The Sample Of Ankara University", *Gazi University, Institute of Educational Sciences Department of the Office of Management Science*, Unpublished Master Thesis, Ankara, 2011.
- [31] Bayram Sezen, "Glass Ceiling Barrier Women Employees Face With in Organizations: A Research On Medium and Large-Scale Hotel Businesses", *18 Mart University, Institute of Social Sciences*, Unpublished Master Thesis, Canakkale, 2008